

Coalescing DevOps with Agile Methodologies in IT Industry; Insights from Case Studies

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Abstract

This study emphasizes collaboratively using Agile methodologies along with DevOps practices for the optimum experience. Although there appear to be advantages to implementing DevOps alongside agile methodologies, practical industry experiences with combining DevOps and agile methodologies are scarce.

Introduction

In the contemporary age of inter - connected, massively scalable systems, technology and research and development necessitates close cooperation among project team members. Software distribution had already altered, as well as repetitive software updates could indeed occur towards the stage where software releases are served concurrently with software usage [1]. In light of the disposition as well as frequency of the releases, potential issues in the production systems must be closely monitored in order to provide the best possible user experience. [1] Software companies must adjust to variations wrought by new principles like DevOps.

Since traditional, plan-driven software development methodologies lack the flexibility to dynamically change the development process, agile techniques were warmly welcomed by the tech industry.

Research from the past demonstrates that alterations to the software development process are complicated organizational change events and cannot be made by simply switching out the current tools and technology for new ones [2]. Those very modifications may have an effect on the organization's structure, culture, and management procedures, among other things. Thus, a critical initial step in organizing and managing such changes is comprehending their overall organizational implications.

Related Research

Most research on this topic is not combined, which means that while there is a lot of research on DevOps capabilities and agile methodologies separately, it is difficult to find research articles that discuss these two topics together. It's ironic, since there are proven benefits to combining these methodologies, and many organizations openly do so. In this research article, case studies done on various organizations by various researchers are gathered to create a research article that elaborates on the benefits of combining DevOps and agile methodologies.

Background to the case

I. Agile Manifesto

It can be identified that in order to deal with the continuous change in user requirements and scopes, agile methodologies became popular.

Agile is an iterative project management & software development approach emphasized on collaboration, customer feedback, and rapid releases. An agile method includes several upfront design & planning and yet developments is done in small batches with tight involvement from stakeholders, which has several advantages, perhaps the most significant being, if software does not meet the expectations of the customer requirements, it can be remedied in real-time. Agile is a set of methodologies, never a single development approach. It is an amalgamation of the systems of practice that developers have used for years, such as scrum, eXtreme Programming (XP), and others. These practitioners came together to combine these approaches into a single set of principles, agile manifesto.

Agile manifesto is comprised with four core values [3] as defined by many & for the ease of reference it is depicted in the diagram below.

Figure 1: Agile Manifesto

II. DevOps

DevOps is a software development methodology which facilitates teams to build, test, and release software more quickly and reliably by integrating agile principles and practices. Both agile and DevOps involve development, testing, and deployment. However, conventional agile misses the mark of operations, that is an essential component of DevOps.

The DevOps concept emerged to integrate the disconnect in-between the development of software and the deployment of that software into production within large software companies.[4] Prime objective of DevOps is to support an agile software development lifecycle by utilizing continuous software development processes such as continuous delivery, continuous deployment, and microservices.[5][6]

Figure 2: DevOps Three Ways

Findings

The agile manifesto and DevOps practices share some similarities and differences.

When agile practices reinforce developer and product management collaborative efforts, DevOps encompasses the ops team.

Agile software development focuses on the spread of concepts to the finalization of code whereas DevOps shifts the emphasis more towards dispatch and maintenance.

When agile underlines incremental approach as well as target applications, whereas DevOps is concerned with test and delivery automation.

Individuals and interactions, working software, customer collaboration, and responding to change have all been consciously taking precedence in the Agile Manifesto.[3] All of those are evidently same primary focus points in DevOps as well, however they have been continued further than the development process to include system and application management.

Discussion

Objectives of agile and DevOps convey similar purposes: improve the speed and quality of application development, and discussing one without the other is illogical. Numerous case studies show agile methodologies to be extremely beneficial, whilst certain organizations have failed to reap the benefits of an agile approach. Reasons for this cause could be due to a variety of factors, including teams not fully understanding or implementing agile practices correctly. It is also possible that incorporating a DevOps approach will help organizations that struggle with agile fill the gaps and achieve the success they desired.

Threats to validity

Regardless of their emerging popularity, there exists a deficit of empirical research on the actual practice of DevOps beyond a discussion of blog posts and industrial surveys [1, 7]. The current literature, aside a handful of case studies [8,] does not provide much insight into the actual implementation and practices of DevOps and their effectiveness in supporting continuous software development.

Conclusion

Agile methods are now an attractive proposition for businesses seeking to enhance the effectiveness, yet were designed primarily for small and individual teams. If presenting agile at a large magnitude, development teams should seamlessly integrate the operations, as well as address the necessity to interface with other organizational units.

DevOps, strategy wherein conventional software engineering aspects have been combined as well as interaction is improved in order to increase the frequency of production releases while maintaining software quality.

DevOps could be viewed as either a transformation of agile practices and perhaps a final link of agile. This is an attempt to bring the agile approach's innovations to processes. At the same time, it's a final link of agile, since such agile principles are only fully realized when DevOps techniques have been used.

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